

Peer Code Review in Research Software: Practices, Improvements, and Implementation Challenges from Interviews of RSEs

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Online Appendix: Tables

This document contains supplementary tables referenced in the paper.

Demographics

Table 1: Participants' Experience as RSEs [B1]

Experience as RSE	Count
1–2 years	6
> 2–5 years	5
> 5–10 years	3
> 10 years	4

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Table 2: Domain Backgrounds of RSE Participants [B2]

Category	Count	Domains
Computer Science / AI	7	Computer Science; AI/ML; Computer Science Infrastructure; Cybersecurity; Human-Computer Interaction
Engineering	4	Mechanical Engineering; Electrical Engineering; Engineering Physics
Physics / Physical Sciences	5	Physics; Astrophysics; Particle Physics; Geophysics; Earth Sciences; Geology; Computational Biophysics; Experimental Physics
Life Sciences / Health	3	Psychology; Neuroscience; Biomedical / Health Sciences
Interdisciplinary	1	Digital Media (Computer Science + Design / Research); Educational Technology

Table 3: Project Domains of RSE Projects [B3]

Category	Count	Domains
Computer Science / Software	5	Software Engineering; Software Infrastructure; AI/ML; Web Development; Statistical Computing
Engineering	4	Mechanical Engineering; Ocean Engineering; Electrical Engineering; Computer Engineering; Signal Processing; Fusion Engineering
Physics / Physical Sciences	5	Physics; Astrophysics; Particle Physics; Astronomy; Quantum Mechanics; Climate Science; Geoscience
Life Sciences / Health	5	Biology; Neuroscience; Medical Image Analysis; Epidemiology; Public Health; Health Measurement
Interdisciplinary / Applied	3	Digital Humanities; Educational Technology; Computational Applied Mathematics; Biophysics; Cryo-EM; Wearable Devices

Table 4: Team Size and Composition of RSE Projects [B4]

Team Category	Composition	Cate-	Count	Description
Solo RSE			3	Single RSE responsible for development with no regular contributors
Small RSE team (2-3 RSEs)			3	Small core RSE group, sometimes supported by a few additional contributors
Medium RSE team (4-6 RSEs)			5	Dedicated RSE team with limited numbers of non-RSE contributors
Large RSE team (7+ RSEs)			1	Large number of RSEs working together
RSE(s) with many contributors	many non-RSE contributors		3	Small RSE core with many additional contributors (e.g., students, researchers, community members)
Variable / unclear RSE count			3	Number of RSEs varied by project or could not be clearly determined

RQ1 Tables

Table 5: Ways to adopt a structured process for code review [Q1]

Category	Count
Pull Request or Platform-based Workflow	19
Defined Review Requirements, Criteria, and Preconditions	15
Informal, Ad-hoc, or Inconsistent Processes	10
Documented Processes, Templates, Norms	7
Steps, Activities, and Review Techniques Used During the Process	6
Borrowed or Adapted Practices	2

Table 6: Characteristics of a code review culture in an organization [Q4].

Category	Count
Consistent Processes, Policies, and Structured Workflows	17
A Supportive, Respectful, and Collaborative Review Environment	12
Shared Technical Knowledge, Expertise, and Review Competence	12
Positive Attitudes Toward Review and a Mature Organizational Mindset	7

Table 7: Availability of clear documentation of review expectations [Q5]

Category	Count
No	14
Yes	4
Partial	2

Table 8: Availability of coding standards [Q6]

Category	Count
No	9
Yes	6
Partial or informal	5

Table 9: Adherence to review expectations or coding standards in projects [Q7]

Category	Count
Followed	12
Not Followed	4
Mixed or Inconsistent	3

Table 10: Ways reviewer–author disagreements are typically handled [Q8].

Category	Count
Authority- or Role-Based Decision Making	9
Informal, Ad-Hoc, or Relationship-Based Handling	8
Synchronous Communication and Live Resolution	7
Discussion-Centered Resolution	7
Structured Processes, Documentation, and Artifacts	4
Respectful Interaction and Professional Conduct	3

Table 11: Ways projects allocate time for code review [Q9].

Category	Count
No Dedicated Time for Code Review	15
Dedicated Time Exists (Formally or Nominally)	6
Code Review Embedded Within Development Workflow	6
Ad Hoc, Availability-Based, or Flexible Allocation	6
Prioritization and Delay Challenges	5
Planned or Accounted-for Review Time	3
Ineffective or Poorly Implemented Review Time	1

Table 12: Ways projects recognize code review contributions [Q10].

Category	Count
No formal recognition or incentives	15
Informal or Social Recognition	6
Recognition Through Authorship or Attribution	5
Implicit or Assumed Credit	2
Tool- or Platform-Based Tracking	4
Documentation-Based Acknowledgment	3
No Recognition or Invisible Work	2

RQ2 Tables

Table 13: Challenges in adopting a structured process for code review [Q1_challenge].

Category	Count
Resource, Time, and Availability Constraints	10
Skill, Training, and Knowledge Gaps	9
Process Adherence, Consistency, and Cultural Challenges	6
Documentation, Setup, and Workflow Barriers	5
Project Characteristics That Limit Structure	5
Tooling, Technology, and Platform Limitations	3

Table 14: Challenges to providing training that improves reviewer effectiveness [Q3_challenge]

Category	Count
Lack of Structured, Formal, or Effective Training	11
Limited Time, Availability, and Competing Responsibilities	8
Cultural, Social, and Confidence-Related Barriers	5
Technical Complexity, Knowledge Gaps, and Hard-to-Teach Areas	5

Table 15: Challenges in establishing a code review culture [Q4a].

Category	Count
Cultural, Mindset, and Social Barriers	19
Time, Resources, and Competing Priorities	15
Process, Tooling, and Standardization Challenges	8
Knowledge, Experience, and Context Barriers	6

Table 16: Reasons review expectations or coding standards are not followed [Q7_why]

Category	Count
Lack of Formal Enforcement Mechanisms	5
Absence or Weakness of Documentation and Explicit Standards	4
Time Pressure and Practical Constraints	2
Others	4

Table 17: Problems caused when review expectations or coding standards are not followed [Q7_problems]

Category	Count
Review Efficiency and Process Overhead	2
Defects and Misunderstandings	2
Inconsistency Across Projects and Teams	1
Code Quality and Compliance Issues	1

Table 18: Difficulties in allocating appropriate time for code review [Q9b].

Category	Count
Time Scarcity and Competing Priorities	7
Availability and Coordination Challenges	4
Prioritization, Focus, and Planning Difficulties	3
Team Size, Expertise, and Resource Limitations	2

Table 19: Reasons projects do not allocate dedicated time for code review [Q9c].

Code Groups	Counts
Perception that Dedicated Time Is Unnecessary	4
Competing Responsibilities and Time Constraints	4
Informal, Ad Hoc, or Unstructured Work Practices	4
Nature of Contributors and Roles	2
Lack of Organizational or Leadership Support	2
Scheduling and Coordination Challenges	2

RQ3 Tables

Table 20: Tool suggestion for research software project [Q2]

Category	Count
Code Hosting Platforms & Pull-Request-Based Review Tools	12
Continuous Integration (CI), Automation, and Build/Test Pipelines	10
Linters, Style Checkers, and Static Analysis Tools	6
Documentation and Artifact Generation Tools	4
Pre-Commit and Local Automation Tools	3
Testing Frameworks	3
Reproducibility, Workflow, and Environment Management Tools	3
IDEs, Platform-Specific, and Domain-Specific Tools	3
AI-Assisted Coding & Review Tools	2
Tools That Are Missing or Not Used	2

Table 21: Training needs to improve reviewer effectiveness [Q3].

Category	Count
Software Engineering, Version Control, and Workflow Training	15
Technical, Domain, and Codebase Understanding	13
Review Skills, Feedback Quality, and Communication Training	12
Experience-Based, Mentorship, and Hands-On Learning	11

Table 22: Strategies to make reviewers more effective beyond training [Q3a].

Category	Count
Tools, Templates, Checklists, and Structured Review Artifacts	10
Mentorship, Pairing, and Experience-Based Learning	8
Improving Reviewer Understanding, Context, and Review Quality	8
Cultural, Collaborative, and Community-Oriented Strategies	5

Table 23: Ways to minimize reviewer-author disagreements [Q8_minimize].

Category	Count
Clarify Review Expectations, Improve Standards, and Contribution Rules	4
Improve Upfront Context and Documentation	2
Align Early Through Design Discussions and Shared Understanding	2
Disagreement May Be Normal or Useful	1
Keep Reviews Professional and Non-Personal	1

Table 24: Additional ways projects should consider recognizing code review contributions [Q10a].

Category	Count
List reviewers in contributors/publication	7
Formal recognition	6
Informal thanks/mentions	4
Internal recognition	3
Github Badges/stars	3
Code review in performance evaluation	3
Public acknowledgements	1